

ISic2906

I.Sicily inscription 2906

Language

Latin

Type

funerary (?)

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Piazza Armerina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Agrigento, Museo Regionale

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645299

EDCS 57100044

Bibliography

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 253

Manganaro, G. 1982. Die Villa von Piazza Armerina, Residenz des kaiserlichen Prokurators, und ein mit ihr verbundenes Emporium von Henna. In Papenfuss, D., Strocka, V.M.(eds.), *Palast und Hütte : Beiträge zum Bauen und Wohnen im Altertum von Archäologen, Vor- und Frühgeschichtlern: Tagungsbeiträge eines*

Symposiums der Alexander von Humboldt-Stiftung, Bonn-Bad Godesberg, veranstaltet vom 25.-30. November 1979 in Berlin. Mainz. pp. 493-513. At 500 no.1
Wilson, R.J.A. 1983. Piazza Armerina. London. At 93

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